

Career development as a predictor of business educators' job performance in universities in South-South, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study was on career development as a predictor of business educators' job performance in Universities in South-South, Nigeria. Three research questions were raised and three hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a correlational survey research design. The population of the study comprised 158 business educators from universities in South-South, Nigeria. All the populations were used since it was manageable. The instrument used was a questionnaire titled Career Development and Job Performance Questionnaire (CDJPQ). The instrument was given to experts in Business Education for content and face validity. The internal consistency of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach alpha with coefficient values of 0.86 and 0.84 for job performance and career development scale respectively. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between career development and business educators' contextual and task performance. Based on the findings, it was recommended that the Management of Universities in South-South, Nigeria should provide regular career development programmes such as training, workshops, and conferences to business educators to update their skills, knowledge, and pedagogy to improve their contextual and task performance.

Keywords: Career development, contextual and task performance, job performance, business educators.

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INTRODUCTION

Business Education programme is a type of education that assists individuals in acquiring skills that can be applied to solve problems in business occupations (Ihekwaba, 2017). It is a part and parcel of Vocational and Technical Education which leads to the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge. Edokpolor and Egbri (2017) defined business education as an educational process that has the primary aim of preparing people for roles in business enterprises as both employers and employees. According to Okoye and Umezulike (2014), business education is part of a vocational education programme that inculcates in individuals business competencies, skills, attitudes,

knowledge and understanding necessary to perform and progress effectively in the business world. Osuala in Nwokike and Okoli (2015), outlined the objectives of business education as follows: (i) To develop in all students the ability to choose discriminately and to use wisely the goods and services that business has to offer. (ii) To assist in developing, on the part of the students, interest in/of the various occupations to be found in the world of business. (iii) To develop in all students the practical way of understanding, and appreciating the actual functioning of our economic system. (iv) To enable students to acquire basic skills in business occupations as beginners who expect to follow business as a career. (v)

To prepare students to enter and succeed in business occupations as beginners who expect to follow business as a career. The attainment of these objectives requires the career development of business educators in order to improve their job performance.

Business educators are responsible for training and teaching students in business-related courses in tertiary institutions such as Polytechnics, Colleges of Education and Universities in Nigeria. Business educators in the course of carrying out their duties, perform different functions. As trained teachers, their primary assignment is that of teaching particularly business education courses offered by students. They are often allocated courses on the basis of their qualifications, experience and staff strength in the department. Parts of their functions also include; supervising students' project, they assess and evaluate students' performance from time to time either in the form of tests, examinations, assignments, assessment of projects, supervision of students on industrial training and teaching practice. They equally, perform administrative duties, attend meetings, carry out research, and attend conferences to keep abreast with current trends in their area of specialization. For business educators to perform these functions effectively, they need to be motivated for career development.

Career development is the total encompassment of an individual's work-related experiences, leading up to the occupational role they may hold within an organization (Stevens and Campion, 2019). Career development is also a process of choosing a career, improving one's skills, and advancing along a career path. It is a lifelong process of learning and decision-making that brings one closer to one's ideal job, skills and lifestyle. Business educators' career development remains a major concern for success and achievement in Universities. Regardless of the skills and knowledge that business educators possess when they commence teaching, maintenance and improvement must be an ongoing process. This is necessary for them to cope with the ever-expanding knowledge base in their subject matter and pedagogy, the rapidly changing social context of schooling, and the increasingly diverse needs of their students. Through career development, business educators can learn these skills to become better and more efficient teachers. Business educators not only give students the best learning experience but also make educators more effective and fulfilled throughout various other aspects of their job. Career development of business educators turns them into stronger and more fitting educators by allowing them to produce useful and personalized lessons for the students and make them more effective in their presentations and course assessments. This can be done through training, seminars, conferences, higher degrees, mentoring and self-directed learning. Therefore, there is a need for career development of business educators in order to ensure effective and efficient job performance.

Job performance is a measure of the extent to which an

employee carries out the various tasks involved in the job. Job performance is a way of achieving a goal or set of goals within an organization. Job performance is the total of an employee's execution of an assigned task. It is also seen as work-related activities expected of an employee and how well those activities were executed, in essence, is an important criterion for organizational outcome. Employee job performance can also be seen as the ability of organizations to keep a workforce that is effective and meets the operational objectives of the organization through the implementation of strategies (Sanyal and Hisam, 2016). The component of business educators' job performance can either be a task or contextual performance. Contextual performance goes beyond formal job responsibilities. Also referred to as "discretionary extra-role behavior" (Bullock, 2013). For instance, the advisory responsibilities of business educators to students, the interaction between colleagues, and student-teacher relationships are components of the contextual performance of business educators in the Universities. Task performance describes the core job responsibilities of an employee. It is also called "in-role prescribed behavior" (Bullock, 2013) and is reflected in specific work outcomes and deliverables as well as their quality and quantity. Essentially, it is about fulfilling the prescribed duties outlined in the job description. Task performance of business educators includes: preparing and delivering lectures, advising students on academics, vocational and career issues, assessing and grading students' class work, assignments, seminars, projects, tests and examination papers, etc. In order to carry out these tasks successfully business educators must possess requisite skills and knowledge.

Statement of the problem

Business educators in tertiary institutions are expected to prepare lecture notes, teach students, and evaluate students' performance before, during and at the end of the semester among other functions. However, the reverse has often been the case as the researcher has in the past observed that some business educators make lectures uninteresting and use instructional materials haphazardly. Sometimes, some do not summarize the main points after the lecture or use few examples or illustrations while teaching. Some have been authoritarian in the course of presenting the lecture, with no discussion during lecture delivery. This may be a result of the poor career development of business educators in universities in South-South, Nigeria. The poor career development appears to contribute to some business educators displaying a lackadaisical attitude to their work which has adversely affected student academic performance. It is against this backdrop that the researcher intends to determine the relationship between career development and job performance of business educators in Universities

in South-South, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study is to examine the relationship between career development and job performance of business educators in tertiary institutions in South-South, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to determine:

1. The relationship between career development and contextual performance of business educators in South-South, Nigeria
2. The relationship between career development and task performance of business educators in South-South, Nigeria.
3. The difference in the relationship between career development and job performance of male and female business educators in Universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Research questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between career development and contextual performance of business educators in South-South, Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between career development and task performance of business educators in South-South, Nigeria?
3. What is the difference in the relationship between career development and job performance of male and female business educators in universities in South-South, Nigeria?

Research hypotheses

Research questions 1 to 3 were hypothesized and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between career development and the contextual performance of business educators.
2. There is no significant relationship between career development and task performance for business educators.
3. There is no significant difference in the relationship between career development and job performance of male and female business educators in Universities in South-South, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational survey research design.

The population of the study comprised 158 business educators from 13 public Universities offering Business Education in South-South, Nigeria. The entire population was used for the study since it was manageable. A structured questionnaire that was divided into two parts was used for data collection. Part A was on the personal data of respondents while part B contained a total of 26 opinion statements designed in a 4-point rating scale ranging from Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Agree (3), and Strongly Agree (4) respectively. The entire questionnaire was correctly filled and returned. The instrument was validated by three experts from the Department of Business Education, University of Benin, Benin City. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined through a pilot test and data collected was analysed using Cronbach Alpha statistics. To achieve this, 15 copies of the questionnaire were administered once to 15 business educators from Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology, Ikere-Ekiti, Ekiti State who were not part of the study's sample. The career development and job performance scale reported a Cronbach Alpha coefficient value of 0.86 and 0.84 respectively which showed that the items in the scale measured were all reliable.

Pearson Correlation Coefficient and Fisher's Z test statistics were used to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule for the research questions was based on r value such that calculated r-value between 0 and 0.20 was regarded as very low correlation, 0.21 and 0.40 was regarded as low correlation, 0.41 and 0.60 was regarded as moderate correlation, 0.61 and 0.80 was regarded as high correlation and 0.81 and 1.00 was regarded as very high correlation (Uzoagulu, 2011). Based on the hypotheses, the probability value (p-value) was used, such that if the p-value was equal to or less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected but if the p-value was greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was retained.

RESULTS

Hypothesis one: There is no significant relationship between career development and the contextual performance of business educators.

Table 1 depicts the relationship between career development and contextual performance of business educators in Public Universities in South-South, Nigeria. From the table the correlation coefficient (r) = .542, this is an indication of a moderate positive relationship between career development and contextual performance. Looking at the p-value (.000) the correlation coefficient is significant testing at .05 alpha levels. Therefore, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected. Hence there is a significant relationship between career development and contextual performance.

Table 1. Pearson R showing the relationship between career development and the contextual performance of business educators.

Variables	N	R	Sig 2-tailed (p-value)	Remarks
Career development Contextual performance	158	.542	.000	Significant

$\alpha = .05, p < .05$

Hypothesis two: There is no significant relationship between career development and task performance of business educators.

Table 2 shows the relationship between career development and task performance of business educators in Public Universities in South-South, Nigeria. From the

table the correlation coefficient (r) = .652, this is an indication of a high positive relationship between career development and task performance. Looking at the p -value (.000) the correlation coefficient is significant testing at .05 alpha levels. Therefore, the null hypothesis is hereby rejected. Hence there is a significant relationship between career development and task performance.

Table 2. Pearson R showing the relationship between career development and task performance of business educators.

Variables	N	R	Sig 2-tailed (p-value)	Remarks
Career development Task performance	158	.652	.000	Significant

$\alpha = .05, p < .05$

Hypothesis three: There is no significant difference in the relationship between career development and task performance of business educators.

Table 3 reveals the difference in the relationship between career development and job performance of male and female business educators in Universities in South-South, Nigeria. From the table the number of males (N) = 86 while

the females (N) = 72 the correlation coefficients (r) = .764 and .736 respectively. The calculated Z -value = 0.35, this value is not significant, testing at .05 alpha levels. The calculated p -value of 0.723 is greater than the alpha level (0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained. This implies that irrespective of sex the relationships between career development and job performance of business educators in universities in South-South, Nigeria are the same.

Table 3. Fisher Z statistic showing the difference in the relationship between career development and job performance of male and female business educators in universities in South-South, Nigeria.

Sex	N	R	Z	P-value	Decision
Male	86	.764	0.35	0.723	Not significant
Female	72	.736			

$\alpha = .05, p > .05$

DISCUSSION

Findings on hypothesis one pointed out that there was a significant relationship between career development and contextual performance of business educators in public Universities in South-South, Nigeria. This implies that when there are appropriate career development strategies such as training, coaching, mentoring, self-directed learning, and promotion of business educators when due, there will be a tendency for better contextual performance. Career development of business

educators will improve their contextual performance such as advisory responsibilities of business educators to students, interaction between colleagues, student-teacher relationship, etc. The findings corroborate the findings of Gray (2021) who reported that Employees are more productive when they are allowed to learn. The current study's findings are similar to Powel (2016) which revealed a significant relationship between training and job performance of secondary school teachers.

Findings on hypothesis two indicated that there was a significant relationship between career development and

task performance of business educators in public Universities in South-South, Nigeria. This implies that when there are sound career development strategies for business educators, they will possess the skills, knowledge and competencies they need to work effectively in a rapidly changing and complex environment. The findings are in line with the findings of Udoh-Uwah and Effanga (2018) who discovered that the career development of business educators contributed to their task performance. The author further affirmed that the career development of business educators will make them meet the criteria for effective tasks. The findings are also consistent with the findings of Adams (2015) who found that career development influences job performance of employees in some selected industries in Lagos State, Nigeria. The author further affirmed that job performance assists them to demonstrate expertise in all job-related tasks, enabling them to be competent in all areas of their job and handling tasks with proficiency as expected.

The findings on hypothesis three indicated that there was no significant difference in the relationship between career development and job performance of male and female business educators. This implies that the relationship between career development and job performance of male business educators is the same as that of female business educators. The current study's findings are similar to that of Le (2022) which revealed that there was no significant difference in the relationship between career development and job performance of male and female teachers in secondary schools.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that career development is related to the job performance of business educators. It is also concluded that there was no significant difference in the relationship between career development and job performance of male and female business educators in universities in South-South, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Consequent to these findings, the study recommends that:

1. Management of universities should organize and promote regular career development programmes such as training, workshops, and conferences for business educators to update their skills, knowledge, and pedagogy to improve their contextual and task performance.
2. Career development programmes should be designed to accommodate all business educators across genders

in all universities in South-South, Nigeria in order to ensure that the benefits of such programmes cut across the gender divide.

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